

Polarographic Behaviour of 6-Methoxybenzothiazolylazo Compounds

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6-Methoxybenzothiazolylazo compounds exhibit a well defined reduction wave at DME in the pH range 2.0–10.0. The products of electrolysis are characterised and a plausible mechanism is suggested for the reduction process.

HETEROCYCLIC azo compounds are known to exhibit interesting reduction behaviour at the DME. Literature survey¹ reveals that polarographic reduction studies on 6-methoxybenzothiazolylazo compounds are not reported earlier. Because of this and in view of the usefulness of these compounds as amperometric reagents for metal analysis, the authors have taken up a detailed study on the polarographic behaviour of 4-(6'-methoxy-2'-benzothiazolylazo)resorcinol (MBTAR), 1-(6'-methoxy-2'-benzothiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (MBTAN) and 4-(6'-methoxy-2'-benzothiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (MBTAN) and 4-(6'-methoxy-2'-benzothiazolylazo)resacetophenone oxime (MBTARPO) in HCl/KCl (pH¹–2), sodium acetate/acetic acid (pH 3–6), ammonium chloride/ammonia (pH 8–10) buffers containing 60% (v/v) dimethylformamide.

Experimental

MBTAR, MBTAN and MBTARPO were synthesised by the reported methods². The purity of the compounds was checked up by tlc. Stock solutions ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) of the compounds were prepared in dimethylformamide (AnalaR). An Elico CL 25 polarograph and Elico pH meter were used. The dropping mercury electrode used had the characteristic $1.80 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $h=80 \text{ cm}$.

Procedure : The buffer solution (6 ml) of desired pH, dimethylformamide (3 ml) and stock solution ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$; 1 ml) of the test compound were taken in the wider limb of the H-cell and the polarograms were recorded after passing pure nitrogen gas for about 15 min to remove dissolved oxygen. Typical polarograms are presented in Fig. 1.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic behaviour of MBTAR and MBTAN :
The results (Table 1) indicate that the compounds

Fig. 1. Polarograms at pH 4 : (a) MBTAR, (b) MBTAN, (c) MBTARPO (first wave) and (d) MBTARPO (second wave).

are reduced in a single well-defined reduction wave in the entire pH range of study. The vulnerable sites in the molecule for reduction are the cyclic $-C=C-$, $-C=N-$ and the exocyclic $-N=N-$ groups. Out of these, the later is more susceptible to reduction compared to the others. The linear dependence of limiting reduction current on the concentration of the compound and the square-root of mercury column height suggests the diffusion-controlled nature of the wave. The low temperature coefficient percentage (1.1%) of the limiting current further supports the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process. The half-wave potential shifts to more negative values with rise in pH of the medium suggesting that the protons are involved in the reduction process. However, the half-wave potential of the wave in alkaline solutions is independent of pH. The shape of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plot is similar to that reported by Zuman³ for cases where both the acidic and basic forms are electroactive but having the same half-wave potentials. It is therefore, concluded that both protonated and unprotonated forms of the compounds reaching the electrode surface are electroactive.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON $E_{1/2}$ AND WAVE HEIGHT

[Substrate] = 1×10^{-3} M, Aqueous dimethylformamide = 60% (v/v)

pH	$-E_{1/2}$ (V) vs SCE					Wave height (μ A)				
	MBTAR	MBTAN		MBTARPO		MBTAR	MBTAN		MBTARPO	
		First wave	Second wave	First wave	Second wave		First wave	Second wave	First wave	Second wave
1.0	0.05	—	0.09	0.04	0.81	3.0	—	2.9	2.5	5.0
2.0	0.12	—	0.14	0.10	0.88	3.0	—	2.9	2.5	4.8
3.0	0.18	—	0.20	0.15	0.94	3.2	—	2.9	2.6	3.9
4.0	0.25	—	0.27	0.21	1.01	3.2	—	3.0	2.6	3.1
5.0	0.32	—	0.33	0.28	1.09	3.1	—	3.0	2.6	2.5
6.0	0.39	—	0.40	0.36	1.14	3.1	—	3.2	2.6	1.9
7.0	0.45	—	0.47	0.42	1.22	3.0	—	2.8	2.6	1.1
8.0	0.50	0.32	0.54	0.50	—	3.0	1.5	2.8	2.4	—
9.0	0.50	0.32	0.54	0.50	—	3.0	1.5	2.8	2.4	—
10.0	0.50	0.32	0.54	0.50	—	3.0	1.5	2.8	2.4	—

Logarithmic analysis of the wave suggests that the wave is irreversible. This fact is further supported by the fact that $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards more negative values with increase in concentration of the compound. The low $K_{f,h}^0$ (heterogeneous rate constant) values and the high ΔG^* (activation free energy) values too lead to the same conclusions. The n (transfer coefficient), ΔG^* , $K_{f,h}^0$ and p (number of protons) MBTAR : 0.54 MBTAN : 0.42 and MBTARPO : 0.67 values are calculated by the usual procedures⁴ (Table 2). The milli-coulometric studies indicate that the number of electrons consumed in the reduction process resulting in the principal wave is two.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

pH	MBTAR	MBTAN	MBTARPO	
			First wave	Second wave
$K_{f,h}^0$ values				
2.0	1.89×10^{-3}	1.74×10^{-3}	4.60×10^{-3}	5.71×10^{-7}
4.0	1.08×10^{-3}	1.51×10^{-3}	5.91×10^{-3}	9.36×10^{-8}
6.0	1.16×10^{-4}	1.39×10^{-4}	1.60×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-10}
8.0	7.47×10^{-4}	1.56×10^{-5}	3.86×10^{-5}	—
10.0	7.47×10^{-4}	1.56×10^{-5}	3.86×10^{-5}	—
ΔG^* values				
2.0	42 608	43 366	39 082	74 366
4.0	46 999	47 692	45 339	81 298
6.0	52 943	53 363	53 743	87 365
8.0	57 617	59 467	61 738	—
10.0	57 617	59 467	61 738	—
α_n values				
2.0	0.35	0.43	0.57	0.43
4.0	0.35	0.43	0.57	0.43
6.0	0.35	0.43	0.57	0.43
8.0	0.35	0.43	0.57	—
10.0	0.35	0.43	0.57	—

The suggested mechanism for the reduction process is presented in Scheme 1.

The wave exhibited by MBTAN at pH > 8.0 is ascribed to the adsorption of the reduction product of the compound at the dropping mercury electrode.

Scheme 1

Polarographic behaviour of TARPO : MBTARPO in contrast to MBTAR and MBTAN, exhibits an additional wave in the pH range 2–7. An examination of the structure of MBTARPO shows that it contains azomethine group. Azomethine group undergoes reduction at more negative potentials than the azo group, and therefore these additional waves at more negative values is attributed to the reduction of the azomethine group. It is confirmed by the usual criteria that the wave is diffusion-controlled and irreversible. A similar wave was reported for resacetophenone oxime⁵. The limiting current decreases rapidly with pH and becomes zero beyond pH 7.0. The studies made at pH 7.0 shows that $i_d/C h^{1/2}$ is not constant suggesting the kinetic controlled nature of the reduction wave. Protonation of the azomethine group is considered responsible for the kinetic behaviour. The number of electrons involved in the reduction process is found to be four by millicoulometric method. The second wave is therefore ascribed to the reduction of the amine,

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